

ISic1165

I.Sicily inscription 1165

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140650

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. [— —] ΚΕ Λ [— — — — — —]
3. [— —] ΜΙΑ [— — — — — —]
4. [— —] ἔζησ [εν ἔτη — —]
5. [— — —] Λ [— — — — — —]
6. [— — — — — — — — — —]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492777

EDCS 39102321

PHI 140650

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0345 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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